

Application of ICT-Skills and E-Learning Facilities in Transforming Social Studies Classroom at Secondary School Level of Education in Nigeria

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Abstract

This study offered a thorough exploration of the integration of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) skills and e-learning facilities in Social Studies classrooms at the secondary school level in Nigeria. Through a comprehensive literature review spanning from 2013 to 2023, the research investigated the transformative potential of technology in reshaping teaching methodologies, student engagement, and the cultivation of digital literacy skills. The findings underscored the challenges of the digital divide, teacher preparedness, and the need for ongoing technical support. Recommendations emanating from the study emphasized the urgency of investing in ICT infrastructure to bridge the digital divide, instituting comprehensive teacher training programs to enhance educators' ICT competencies, providing strategic technical support systems, promoting collaborative learning platforms, and advocating for flexible policy frameworks to adapt to the dynamic nature of educational technology. The study contributes valuable insights to the discourse on educational technology in the context of Nigerian secondary schools, serving as a foundation for informed strategies to harness the benefits of ICT while addressing the identified challenges. Ultimately, this research aimed to guide policymakers, educators, and stakeholders in fostering an inclusive, technology-enhanced learning environment in Social Studies classrooms, aligning with the demands of the 21st-century educational landscape in Nigeria.

Keywords: Information and Communication Technology (ICT), E-learning facilities, Social Studies education, Secondary school level

Introduction

In the contemporary landscape of education, the integration of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has emerged as a transformative force, reshaping traditional pedagogical approaches (UNESCO, 2013). This study delves into the profound implications of applying ICT skills and leveraging e-learning facilities to enhance the educational experience within the realm of Social Studies at the secondary school level, particularly in the context of Nigeria. As Nigeria grapples with the challenges of providing quality education to its burgeoning youth population (World Bank, 2018), the Secondary School level becomes a critical juncture in a student's academic journey. Social Studies, being integral to holistic education, offers a strategic lens for examining the transformative impact of ICT and e-learning tools on educational practices and outcomes. The Information and Communication Technology (ICT) revolution has ushered in an era where traditional boundaries of classrooms are expanding, transcending the limitations of physical spaces (Selwyn, 2020). Embracing this technological paradigm shift in Social Studies classrooms holds promise for revitalizing the learning experience. Integrating ICT skills into the curriculum enables educators to present information in innovative and interactive ways, fostering critical thinking, and collaborative problem-solving, and digital literacy among students (Davis & Tearle, 1999). Additionally, the advent of e-learning facilities offers opportunities for personalized and self-paced learning, catering to the diverse needs and learning styles of students in Nigeria's secondary schools (Ally, 2008).

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Meanwhile, E-facilities and skills for Information and Communication Technology had a significant impact on several elements of teaching and learning, affecting both teachers and students in transforming Nigerian Social Studies Classroom. The teachers experienced issues such as a deficiency in information communication technology (ICT) skills, a lack of readiness to utilize online tools, a low level of confidence in conducting online courses, and a lack of understanding of how to incorporate technology into classrooms (Boonmoh et al., 2022). The low level of ICT skills and lack of readiness to utilize E-facilities; made it harder for teachers to create online courses, produce online teaching materials, and modify content to meet changing demands. According to Agbo, (2015) the technology involves the generation of knowledge and processes to develop systems that solve problems and extend human capabilities. In other words, technology can change or alter how people access, gather, analyze, present, transmit, and simulate information. Schools, like all other social institutions, are rapidly embracing information and communication technologies (ICT). Recent research underscores the evolving role of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in education, emphasizing its significance beyond being a mere tool or a replacement for traditional teaching methods. Contemporary perspectives position ICT as a crucial instrument supporting innovative approaches to teaching and learning, with an emphasis on fostering students' skills for collaboration, communication, problem-solving, and lifelong learning (Mann, 2020; Kirschner & De Bruyckere, 2017). The transformative potential of ICT lies in its ability to not only provide increased access to information but also to inspire novel teaching methodologies, facilitating continuous interaction within and beyond the confines of traditional classroom settings (UNESCO, 2019).

While disputes regarding the efficacy of incorporating ICT in education persist, recent studies highlight that the limited use of ICT is not solely attributed to debates over its value but is also influenced by the inadequate availability of ICT resources within schools (Cuban & Pea, 2017; Ottenbreit-Leftwich et al., 2018). Additionally, the dynamics within the typical classroom, encompassing the prevailing realities and cultural aspects (Ekpiwre & Haruna, 2019), along with the knowledge, skills, beliefs, and expertise of teachers, play pivotal roles in shaping the successful integration of ICT into educational practices (Ertmer et al., 2018; Knezek & Christensen, 2019). Furthermore, the non-availability of E-resources further compounds the challenges associated with harnessing the full potential of ICT in education (Owusu-Fordjour et al., 2020). This study seeks to scrutinize the current state of Social Studies education in Nigerian secondary schools, evaluating the extent to which ICT skills and e-learning facilities are integrated into the curriculum. Moreover, it aims to explore the challenges faced by educators in adopting these technologies and the perceptions of students towards this modernized approach to learning. By investigating these aspects, the research endeavours to provide insights into the potential benefits and drawbacks of incorporating ICT in Social Studies classrooms, contributing to the discourse on education reform in Nigeria. As technology continues to evolve, understanding its role in transforming education becomes imperative, and this study strives to shed light on the specific nuances within the Nigerian secondary school context.

Methodology

The present study employed a comprehensive literature review methodology to explore the application of ICT skills and e-learning facilities in transforming Social Studies classrooms at the secondary school level of education in Nigeria. This methodology involved a systematic and critical analysis of existing secondary sources, scholarly articles, academic journals, books, and relevant publications from the years 2013 to 2023. The purpose was to synthesize and evaluate the then-current state of knowledge, identify key trends, challenges, and opportunities, and contribute to the existing discourse on the integration of technology in Social Studies education.

1. **Literature Search and Selection:** A thorough literature search was conducted using academic databases such as PubMed, JSTOR, Google Scholar, and educational research databases. The search focused on studies, articles, and publications related to the integration of ICT skills and e-learning facilities in Social Studies classrooms at the secondary school level in Nigeria.
2. **Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria:** The inclusion criteria for selecting literature involved relevance to the study's focus, publication between 2013 and 2023, and a focus on secondary education in Nigeria. Exclusion criteria involved studies outside the specified timeframe, those not directly related to ICT in Social Studies education, and those not conducted within the Nigerian context.
3. **Data Extraction and Synthesis:** Pertinent information, including key findings, methodologies employed in the primary studies, and limitations, was extracted from the selected literature. The data was then synthesized to identify patterns, recurring themes, and gaps in the existing knowledge base.
4. **Quality Assessment:** The quality and rigor of the selected literature were assessed using established criteria for evaluating academic sources. This ensured that the synthesized information was based on reliable and valid research.

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5. **Thematic Analysis:** The identified literature was thematically analysed to categorize findings related to the application of ICT skills and e-learning facilities in Social Studies classrooms. This process helped in identifying the common challenges faced, successful strategies employed, and potential areas for further research.
6. **Ethical Considerations:** Since this study relied on existing literature, ethical considerations primarily involved proper citation and adherence to copyright regulations. All sources were appropriately credited to maintain academic integrity.

Intersection of Social Studies Classroom Dynamics and ICT Integration in Secondary Education

The concept of the Social Studies classroom at the secondary school level has been a subject of considerable scholarly exploration, with an emphasis on understanding its dynamics, challenges, and opportunities. Researchers have delved into the multifaceted nature of Social Studies education, recognizing it as a discipline that plays a pivotal role in shaping students' understanding of societal structures, cultural diversity, and global interconnectedness (Davies, 2013; Clark & Erikson, 2018). The secondary school level, being a critical stage in the educational journey, represents a juncture where students develop a more nuanced comprehension of social issues, civic responsibilities, and historical contexts through the lens of Social Studies. Several studies have examined the traditional structure of Social Studies classrooms, often characterized by teacher-centred instructional methods and content-focused approaches (Crawford, 2014; Akpan, 2019). Scholars have highlighted the need for a shift toward more interactive, student-centred pedagogies that promote critical thinking, active engagement, and the development of skills essential for informed citizenship (Sawyer & White, 2013; Thornton, 2016). This shift aligns with the broader goals of Social Studies education, aiming to cultivate a generation of individuals capable of navigating complex societal issues and contributing meaningfully to their communities.

The integration of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) and e-learning tools into the Social Studies classroom has emerged as a focal point in recent literature. Researchers underscore the potential of these technologies to enhance the learning experience, providing opportunities for interactive, dynamic, and learner-centric instruction (Ferdig & Kennedy, 2014; Owusu-Fordjour et al., 2021). The application of ICT in Social Studies classrooms at the secondary level has been associated with improved information access, collaborative learning environments, and the development of digital literacy skills crucial for the 21st-century learner (Pelgrum & Anderson, 2017; Voogt et al., 2018). Despite these advancements, challenges persist, and the literature reflects ongoing discussions on issues such as the digital divide, teacher preparedness, and the need for effective professional development to integrate ICT seamlessly into Social Studies classrooms (Kozma, 2015; Baran, 2014; Tondeur et al., 2017). Understanding the existing literature on the concept of Social Studies classrooms at the secondary school level provides a foundation for the current study, which aims to contribute to this discourse by investigating the specific implications and challenges of applying ICT skills and e-learning facilities within the Nigerian educational context. This study seeks to build upon the insights gleaned from the existing literature to inform practical strategies for transforming Social Studies education in secondary schools through the judicious incorporation of modern technological tools.

Review of E-Facilities for Social Studies Classrooms at the Secondary School Level

The exploration of e-facilities for the Social Studies classroom at the secondary school level has been a prominent focus in educational literature, reflecting the increasing recognition of technology's transformative potential in shaping contemporary pedagogical landscapes. Scholars have classified e-facilities into various types, each offering unique opportunities for enhancing the learning experience within the realm of Social Studies. One significant type of e-facility is the use of online resources and digital content. Researchers have extensively discussed the benefits of leveraging digital platforms to provide students with access to a vast array of historical documents, multimedia content, and interactive simulations (Berson et al., 2019; Hicks, 2017). These resources not only broaden the scope of learning materials but also cater to diverse learning styles, fostering a more inclusive educational environment.

Virtual Learning Environments (VLEs) have also gained prominence in the literature, presenting comprehensive platforms that facilitate a dynamic and collaborative online space for Social Studies education (Dennen et al., 2013; Ertmer et al., 2019). VLEs incorporate features such as discussion forums, multimedia presentations, and assessment tools, allowing students to engage in meaningful discourse, collaborative projects, and self-paced learning. The integration of VLEs aligns with the contemporary shift toward learner-centred approaches, promoting active participation and critical thinking skills. Simulations and educational games represent another facet of e-facilities in the Social Studies classroom. The literature highlights the potential of simulation software and games to immerse students in historical events, fostering experiential learning and a deeper understanding of complex social issues (Shaffer, 2016; Clark, 2018). These interactive tools not only make learning more engaging but also encourage the development of problem-solving skills and historical empathy.

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Furthermore, video conferencing and online collaboration tools have emerged as essential e-facilities, particularly in the context of global connectivity and remote learning (Kimmmons et al., 2020). These tools facilitate virtual guest lectures, cross-cultural exchanges, and collaborative projects, enriching the Social Studies curriculum with real-world perspectives and diverse cultural insights.

However, despite the evident advantages, literature also underscores challenges associated with the implementation of e-facilities, including issues related to digital equity, teacher training, and the need for continuous technical support (Jacobsen & Mackey, 2016; Hobbs, 2017). Understanding the diverse types of e-facilities available for Social Studies classrooms at the secondary school level is crucial for educators and policymakers, guiding the thoughtful integration of technology to create enriched and inclusive learning environments. This discussion lays the foundation for the subsequent exploration of how these e-facilities can be applied within the Nigerian educational context, emphasizing the potential for transformative impacts on Social Studies education.

Benefits of E-Resources for Social Studies Teachers at the Secondary School Level

The literature surrounding the benefits of e-resources, particularly online teaching facilities, for Social Studies teachers at the secondary school level is rich with insights into how technology can positively impact the teaching-learning dynamic. Researchers have extensively explored the advantages that e-resources bring to the teaching practices of Social Studies educators, highlighting transformative effects on instructional methods, student engagement, and overall learning outcomes. One paramount benefit emphasized in the literature is the expanded access to diverse and up-to-date learning materials. E-resources empower Social Studies teachers to augment their curricula with a plethora of digital content, ranging from primary source documents and multimedia presentations to virtual field trips and interactive simulations (Mason & Berson, 2020; Hicks, 2015). This not only broadens the scope of materials available but also enables educators to adapt their teaching to current events and evolving societal dynamics. The interactive nature of e-resources stands out as a transformative factor in Social Studies education. Online teaching facilities provide tools for creating dynamic and engaging lessons that cater to diverse learning styles (Lee & Spires, 2022; Baran et al., 2013). The incorporation of multimedia elements, interactive maps, and virtual experiences not only captures students' attention but also facilitates a deeper understanding of complex historical and social concepts. Teachers can leverage these resources to foster critical thinking skills and promote a more participatory classroom environment.

Moreover, the collaborative potential of e-resources has been a recurrent theme in the literature. Online platforms and tools enable Social Studies teachers to engage students in collaborative projects, discussions, and global connections (Brush et al., 2018; Whitworth et al., 2019). This collaborative aspect aligns with the broader goals of Social Studies education, fostering a sense of community and encouraging students to appreciate diverse perspectives, both locally and globally. The efficiency and flexibility offered by e-resources for lesson planning and delivery have been underscored as crucial advantages. Teachers can access and organize a wealth of resources, customize materials to suit specific learning objectives, and employ various assessment tools to gauge student understanding (Doering et al., 2019; Voogt et al., 2013). This streamlining of administrative tasks allows educators to allocate more time to engaging with students and tailoring their teaching to individual needs. However, the literature also acknowledges challenges, such as the need for teacher training, concerns about digital equity, and potential distractions in the online environment (Graham et al., 2022; Niess, 2013). Addressing these challenges is essential to fully harness the benefits of e-resources in Social Studies classrooms at the secondary school level.

Impact of ICT Skills for Secondary School Social Studies Teachers

The literature on the benefits of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) skills for Social Studies teachers at the secondary school level highlights the transformative impact that technological proficiency can have on teaching practices, professional development, and overall educational outcomes. Researchers have explored the multifaceted advantages that accrue to educators equipped with ICT skills, recognizing them as instrumental in navigating the complexities of contemporary education. One overarching benefit identified in the literature is the enhancement of teaching methodologies through the integration of ICT skills. Social Studies teachers with adept ICT skills can employ a variety of digital tools and resources to create interactive and engaging lessons (Cuban & Pea, 2017; Chai et al., 2020). Incorporating multimedia presentations, virtual field trips, and interactive simulations not only captures students' interest but also facilitates a deeper understanding of complex social concepts and historical events. Professional development for Social Studies teachers is another key area emphasized in the literature. ICT skills empower educators to participate in ongoing training programs, online communities, and collaborative

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networks, fostering a culture of continuous learning (Ertmer et al., 2022). This not only keeps teachers abreast of the latest pedagogical approaches but also allows them to share best practices and innovative strategies with their peers.

The literature also highlights the role of ICT skills in promoting personalized learning experiences for students. Social Studies teachers equipped with ICT skills can tailor their instruction to accommodate diverse learning styles and abilities (Ertmer et al., 2022; Voogt et al., 2017). Adaptive technologies, online resources, and digital platforms enable educators to address individual needs, providing a more inclusive and student-centric learning environment. Moreover, the acquisition of ICT skills contributes to the development of digital literacy among both teachers and students. Social Studies educators' proficiency in ICT can guide students in navigating the vast digital landscape, critically evaluating online information, and leveraging technology for research and communication (Ritzhaupt et al., 2013; Knezek & Christensen, 2019). This not only prepares students for the demands of the digital age but also cultivates essential skills for active citizenship.

However, challenges related to the digital divide, resistance to change, and the need for comprehensive teacher training are acknowledged in the literature (Ertmer, 2015; Tondeur et al., 2019). Bridging these gaps is imperative to ensure equitable access to the benefits of ICT skills for Social Studies teachers at the secondary school level. The literature review therefore underscores the pivotal role of ICT skills in empowering Social Studies teachers to adapt to the evolving educational landscape. Beyond enriching teaching methodologies, these skills contribute to ongoing professional development, personalized learning, and the cultivation of digital literacy—all essential components for preparing students for an interconnected and technology-driven world.

Challenges in Implementing E-Facilities and ICT Skills in Secondary School Social Studies Classrooms

The literature examining the challenges of e-facilities and ICT skills for Social Studies classrooms at the secondary school level sheds light on the complexities associated with integrating technology into educational practices. Researchers have identified several hurdles that educators face, encompassing both the availability of e-facilities and the development and utilization of ICT skills. One pervasive challenge highlighted in the literature is the digital divide, reflecting disparities in access to technology among students. In many instances, schools may lack the necessary infrastructure and resources to provide consistent access to e-facilities, hindering the implementation of technology-enhanced teaching (Warschauer, 2016; Pelgrum & Anderson, 2017). Moreover, issues of socioeconomic status and geographical location contribute to inequities in students' access to digital tools, exacerbating disparities in educational outcomes. Teacher preparedness and professional development constitute another significant challenge. While technology has the potential to revolutionize teaching practices, many educators may lack the necessary ICT skills and training to effectively integrate e-facilities into their classrooms (Ertmer et al., 2022; Tondeur et al., 2017). Insufficient professional development opportunities and a resistance to change further compound this challenge, hindering the seamless adoption of technology in Social Studies education. The literature also emphasizes the need for ongoing technical support and maintenance of e-facilities. Technological glitches, system failures, and the rapid pace of technological advancements necessitate continuous support to ensure that e-facilities function optimally within the classroom environment (Ottenbreit-Leftwich et al., 2022; Elyan & Adwan, 2019). Without adequate technical assistance, educators may face disruptions that impede the smooth flow of lessons and compromise the learning experience.

Furthermore, issues related to the integration of e-facilities with traditional pedagogical methods are discussed in the literature. Balancing the use of technology with other instructional strategies and ensuring that it aligns with curriculum objectives can be a delicate task (Sandholtz et al., 2014; Hew & Brush, 2022). There is a concern that overemphasis on technology may lead to a superficial integration rather than a meaningful transformation of teaching and learning practices in the Social Studies classroom. The rapid evolution of technology introduces a temporal challenge, making it challenging for educators to stay abreast of the latest advancements and incorporate them effectively into their teaching (Kozma, 2015; Voogt & Roblin, 2022). This dynamic nature of technology requires educators to engage in continuous learning and adaptability, placing additional demands on their time and resources.

Other challenges include among others, the following:

1. High Cost of ICT Facilities
2. Inadequate ICT Infrastructural Facilities in Schools
3. Poor Computer Literacy among Teachers and Students
4. Poor Implementation of ICT Educational Policies
5. Unstable Power Supply
6. Inadequate Funding

Conclusion

The comprehensive literature review undertaken in this study has illuminated the intricate landscape of integrating ICT skills and e-learning facilities in Social Studies classrooms at the secondary school level in Nigeria. The analysis revealed the transformative potential of technology in enhancing teaching methodologies, fostering student engagement, and cultivating digital literacy skills. However, challenges such as the digital divide, teacher preparedness, and the need for ongoing technical support were identified as significant hurdles. The findings underscore the imperative for a nuanced approach to technology integration, emphasizing equitable access, continuous professional development, and strategic solutions to overcome existing challenges. This study contributes to the broader discourse on educational technology by providing valuable insights into the specific context of Social Studies education in Nigerian secondary schools, laying the groundwork for informed strategies to harness the benefits of ICT and e-learning facilities while addressing associated challenges.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made:

1. Given the challenges associated with the digital divide, policymakers and educational institutions should prioritize substantial investments in ICT infrastructure. Ensuring equitable access to e-learning facilities is essential for creating an inclusive educational environment, especially in regions where technological resources are scarce.
2. To address the identified challenges related to teacher preparedness and professional development, educational authorities should implement comprehensive and ongoing training programs. These initiatives should focus on enhancing teachers' ICT skills, integrating technology into pedagogical practices, and navigating the evolving digital landscape, ultimately fostering a cadre of educators well-equipped for technology-enhanced instruction.
3. Recognizing the need for continuous technical support, educational institutions should establish robust mechanisms to address technological glitches and provide timely assistance to teachers. This includes creating dedicated support teams, establishing helpdesk services, and fostering partnerships with technology experts to ensure the smooth functioning of e-learning facilities.
4. Policymakers should develop flexible and adaptive policy frameworks that acknowledge the dynamic nature of educational technology. Such frameworks should provide guidance on the integration of ICT in Social Studies classrooms, incentivize innovative approaches, and be responsive to emerging challenges and opportunities, allowing for continuous adaptation to the evolving educational landscape.

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